

Educational Level of Parents and Its Effect on Hb level of early adolescent Girls

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Introduction

Early adolescence is the second critical period of life in human beings with rapid physical growth, changes in body composition, physiology and endocrine. Rapid physical growth and changes in body composition heighten their nutritional requirements to avoid risk of under nutrition. In Adolescence, girls have a rapid increase in both muscle mass and blood volume. The menstruation adds nutrient burden so it is important in adolescence to get proper food and good nutrition essential for survival, physical growth, mental development, performance and productivity, health and well being of adolescents' girls. The current nutritional status of early adolescent girls will decide the well being of the present as well as the future generations. Under nutrition among these girls is associated with reduced lean body mass, lack of muscular strength and decreased work capacity.

Objective of the study

The objectives of the present study are: -

1. To correlate parent education level and its relation with Hb level of early adolescent Girls.
2. To evaluate the nutrition status of selected adolescence girls.
3. To find out dietary consumption pattern of early adolescent girls.

Methodology of Study

The present study comprises of assessing the nutritional status and Hb level of 300 adolescence girls belonging to 13 to 15years of age group and their Parents Education level. Information regarding adolescent's girls was collected by personal interview by the researcher with a pre-planned questionnaire. Hemoglobin estimation was done by the Sahli's method.

Result

Literacy level of family members of participant adolescent girls given in Table No. 1. 39% families have their literacy level up to secondary school level and near to 34% families have literacy up to secondary school level education. Only 20% families of participant of adolescent girls have college level education and 7% families have university level education. The correlation between parental education and girl's hemoglobin is higher than higher education and proper hemoglobin levels. It was seen that whose parents are highly educated in that girls the hemoglobin level was found to be good. Table no.2 shows educational level of parents and mean of Hb level of early adolescent girls.

Table No. 1: - Distribution of sample is according to Parental Educational Level.

Educational Level	Sangli (N=279)	Percentage	Kolhapur (N=300)	Percentage
Std. 7	17	6	14	5
Std. 10	94	33.69	95	32
Std. 12	95	34.05	110	37
U.G.	56	20.07	59	20
P.G.	17	6.09	22	7

Table No. 2: - Educational Level of Sample Parents and Mean and Standard Deviation of Hb level of early adolescent Girls

Education Level	MEAN	SD
Std. 7	8.85	0.564129
Std. 10	9.78	0.618206
Std. 12	9.93	0.62491
UG	10.27	0.628748
PG	10.28	0.693507

Discussion

This study examines relationships between Parents educational level, their nutrition knowledge, adolescent's dietary intake and Hb level of adolescent's girls. Lack of nutrition knowledge does impact on diet of adolescent girls. Many studies reveal that in developing countries, anaemia is likely the largest nutritional problem in adolescents. Iron deficiency is the most widespread form of micronutrient malnutrition. Adolescents need to be included in presented anaemia, and iron (and folate) programmes of the health sector the health of adolescents, with the focus on improving knowledge, skills, access to counseling and health services, and safety and support of the environment. An adolescent who are found to be at increased nutritional risk should be assessed in greater detail to determine the specific nutrition related behaviors, that need to be addressed through education and counseling. Health educations strategies focus on health risks are therefore unlikely to be effective in adolescents. Television and other multimedia were an important source of information on food and nutrition, along with parents and schools. The coverage of educational systems is larger than the health system for school-age populations, at least in urban population. Strives to improve the health of school personnel, families and community members as well as students; and works with community leaders to help them understand how the community contributes to health and education. The present study focus on parent's educational level of early adolescent girl's and nutritional status of early adolescent girl's and its impact on their health status which has direct impact on the quality of the future generation.

Recommendation and Suggestions

Nutrition awareness in adolescent girls and their parents and its impact on adolescent's health should be assessed.

1. Use the multimedia (Which is very effective source) for give the nutrition knowledge to adolescents and their parents.
2. Made pamphlets on nutrition and diet and distributes these through schools and anganwadis to adolescent girls and their mother for awareness about food and nutrition.
3. Invention of low cost food sources and combination of foods for prevent anemia in adolescent girls.
4. Awareness must be created among the school and college students regarding junk food and its impact on health.

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